

HOW TO START USING MINKA

- Create your account on MINKA and register your observations.

- Photograph what you see.

- Upload the photos to MINKA and check that the place and date you made the observation have been recorded.

- Try to identify which organism it is, but if you don't know, the MINKA community will help you.

UPLOAD OBSERVATIONS FROM SMARTPHONE

- Click on the "more" button.

- Upload your observation by choosing one of the 3 options:
 a) Upload without image (it will not achieve research grade).
 b) Upload from your mobile phone gallery (upload a photo you've already taken).
 c) Upload from camera (take a new photo).

- If the image has metadata and/or location, it will ask if you want to use it.

- If you don't have a location in the metadata, you can select it on the map or use the location of your mobile phone if you took the photo with it.

- Suggest the name of a species if you know it. If you don't know how to identify it, the MINKA community will help you.

- You can also add more photos of the same organism seen from different angles to the same observation to help the community determine the species in question.

- Once the observation has been uploaded, you will be asked if you want to go to the main menu or upload more observations.

- If you want to record more observations from the same day and place, you will be asked if you want to keep the same location and date of the previous observation.

- If you don't have an Internet connection, you can generate new observations. Once you have access to them again, you can sync them individually or all at once and they will be incorporated.

UPLOAD OBSERVATIONS FROM MINKA'S WEBSITE

- Select the "Upload" option.

- Select or drag the images you want to upload.

- The platform will automatically read the metadata (date and location) if the images have them.

- Indicate the location individually or select a group of images to put a joint location:

Individual Location: Select Location for each observation.

Group Location: Select the Location option from the left menu.

- On the map, you can select the point where the observation was made, make the radius larger or smaller and select whether the observation is open (everyone sees it), obscured (the exact point is not visible) or private (only MINKA administrators see it).

- You can also save frequent observation points and give them a name.

- Later, the list of saved places will appear on the top bar of the map.

- If you know what species it is, write its name.

- All that remains is to publish the observations. If you publish observations without identification or without a date or location, the system will alert you with a message, but you can publish them anyway.

IDENTIFY OBSERVATIONS OF OTHER MINKA USERS

- Click on the "Identify" menu in the header of the MINKA website.

- In the "Identify" section you will see all the observations from members of the MINKA community that need to be identified or that need help with the identification. You can help to identify species that you know well, agree with the identification of other members or even propose a new identification by clicking on the observation.

- Once you click on an observation in the "Identify" list, you can add an identification or even add a comment if you want to ask something to the author of the observation.

JOIN AN EXISTING PROJECT

- Search for a project in the "Community" section of the header.

- Or write the URL of the project you're looking for in your browser. In our case: https://minka-sdg.org/projects/testing_greece_2022
- Click the button "Join".

- Now, there are two options to upload observations to this project:
 a. Selecting the project when uploading a new observation

b. Going to your observations section, clicking on the observation you want to add, and adding the project into the field "project".

CREATE A NEW PROJECT

- Go to the "Project" page in the "Community" section of the header.

- Click the button "Start a Project".

- You can now create a "Collection Project" or a "Principal Project".
 For example, imagine you and your students want to study the trees around your school. You can create a "Collection Project" for each grade collecting pictures and then create a "Principal Project" that contains all the projects of your school.

Research grade: To get the "research grade" in an observation, more than 2/3 of the MINKA community commenting on this observation must agree on its identification. If there is no consensus, the observation will not have the identification as a species, but the MINKA algorithm will search the identification grade where the 2/3 agrees. For example, imagine that a user says that one observation is *Labrus viridis*, but another user says that it is *Labrus merula*. There is no consensus on the identification of the species in the observation, but both users agree that the gender is *Labrus*, so 2/3 agrees on that. Therefore, the observation will reach the research level with the gender *Labrus* and it will be uploaded to global data repositories with this gender identification.

If you see an observation identified as a species but you are aware that this species cannot be identified just by a picture (it needs genetic confirmation, for example), you can propose a gender.

MINKA has its own data curators, scientists and researchers specialized in taxonomy that validate most of the data uploaded to the platform.